

IMPROVING STUDENT ENGAGEMENT IN ENGLISH CLASSROOM**Shahnoza Berdiyeva Xolmaxmatovna**

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Abstract. Improvements in technology creates new opportunity and challenges not only in societies, but also in educational settings. Consequently, many pedagogical approaches have been introduced to meet student's needs. Regarding the need for new pedagogical approaches in L2 settings to improve student's essential skills, flipped learning approach has gained considerable attention from many language teachers, educators and researches. This article intends to provide a theoretical. This article intends to give readers a theoretical basis and demonstrate how the flipped learning approach can be used in English classrooms to improve students' engagement and other 21st-century abilities. Additionally, it attempts to emphasize challenges when employed.

Key words: flipped classroom, flipped learning, educational settings, new pedagogical approaches, technology creates.

**ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ВОВЛЕЧЕННОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ В ЗАНЯТИЯХ
АНГЛИЙСКИМ ЯЗЫКОМ**

Аннотация. Совершенствование технологий создает новые возможности и проблемы не только в обществе, но и в образовательных учреждениях. Следовательно, многие педагогические подходы были введены для удовлетворения потребностей учащихся. Что касается необходимости новых педагогических подходов в условиях L2 для улучшения основных навыков учащихся, перевернутый подход к обучению привлек значительное внимание многих учителей иностранных языков, педагогов и исследователей. Эта статья предназначена для предоставления теоретических. Эта статья призвана дать читателям теоретическую основу и продемонстрировать, как перевернутый подход к обучению можно использовать на уроках английского языка для улучшения вовлеченности учащихся и других способностей 21-го века. Кроме того, он пытается подчеркнуть проблемы при работе.

Ключевые слова: перевернутый класс, перевернутое обучение, образовательные установки, новые педагогические подходы, технологии создают.

Introduction. Flipped learning, an alternate strategy that incorporates the use of technology outside the classroom, has gained significant interest from academics and instructors all around the world. Furthermore, English language educators and teachers accept this cutting-edge strategy as one of the options when creating their lesson plans for the classroom. This article emphasizes the four pillars of flipped learning, the components, and characteristics of the flipped learning classroom while providing a brief history, theoretical background, and underlying principles. Studies on using the flipped learning approach in various English classroom settings where English is regarded as a second and/or foreign language are also included, as well as studies on how the flipped learning approach improves learners' engagement and 21st century skills. The next section discusses and offers the specifics.

Flipped learning has been used in the field of English as a foreign language (EFL) to assist students learn more English idioms and to encourage their active learning by making them more motivated to communicate, improving their speaking abilities, and feeling more satisfied with the flip approach (Hung, 2017). Other EFL-related areas, such as English speaking (Li & Suwanthep, 2017), English writing (Ahmed, 2016), and reading comprehension (Abaeian & The Asian Journal of Applied Linguistics 171), have also looked into the effects of flipped learning.

History. When Salma Khan used the phrase "Flip your class" in a 2010 TED Talk or "Technology, Entertainment, Design Talk," or when Jon Bergmann and Aaron Sams published a book in 2012, flipped learning gained widespread recognition. However, Wesley Baker's 2000 academic study on learning management systems, often known as LMS, is when the term "Flipped" or "Flipping" was originally used.

The phrase reappeared in the scholarly study conducted by Tenneson and McGlasson in 2005. They described the flipped classroom as a blended learning environment that makes use of technology to provide students more time for engaged discussion (Tenneson & McGlasson, 2005).

Later in 2007, Jeremy Strayer completed his doctoral dissertation with a focus on contrasting the educational activities in a typical classroom with those in a flipped classroom using an intelligent tutoring system. In 2012, he published his research on how instruction in an inverted classroom may affect collaboration, innovation, and task orientation. He has since continued to study the use of flipped learning (Strayer, 2007, 2012). Due to the proximity of the school to their homes in Woodland Park, Colorado, Jon Bergmann and Aaron Sams discovered that absences were common throughout the same time period. As a result, they started looking for strategies to reach every student and started "vodcasting" videos for them (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). The outcome of this innovative idea suggested that the students had improved their exam outcomes. Eventually the flipped classroom become recognizable and was approved by many academics and teachers all around the world.

Theoretical background. Flipped learning approach stems from constructivist learning theory, which stresses students' roles in learning by assisting them in becoming active learners and increasing their participation in classes, serves as the foundation for the flipped learning approach. The benefit of a flipped learning approach is that it converts class time into learning activities where students ask questions about the material, collaborate with one another in practical exercises, and test their knowledge by applying what they have learned in class to real-world scenarios.

Four pillars. Experienced educators in this sector have identified the building blocks of a flipped classroom that enable flipped learning to take place in order to explain the idea behind the flipped learning approach. These include Professional Educator, Intentional Content, Flexible Environment, and Learning Culture (Flipped Learning Network, 2014).

A flipped classroom's learning environment is characterized by the introduction of several learning modes such as group work, independent study, research, performance, and project work that maximize students' learning potential. By participating in various learning contexts, students can select when and where to learn, which can progressively and gradually improve their level of autonomy.

A shift in Learning Culture. Since we entered the 21st century, there has been a change from a teacher-centered to a student-centered approach when discussing a shift in learning culture. In flipped classrooms, students have a fantastic learning opportunity and can explore the subjects deeply. Additionally, both inside and outside of the classroom, students are actively involved in acquiring new information or skills. They can take responsibility for their own education and learn at their own pace. Teachers might highlight the use of classroom interactions in the meanwhile to make sure that students understand each subject.

Intentional Content. In a flipped classroom, the teachers have a significant role in what they need to teach students directly and what resources they should use to encourage independent exploration outside of the classroom. In order to make the most of class time, teachers choose specific content that gives students the opportunity to experience a variety of teaching strategies, depending on the subject matter and grade level of the students, such as active learning, peer instruction, inquiry-based learning, project-based learning, or problem-based learning.

Professional teachers. Experienced, competent, and professional teachers are more needed than ever because it is critical to carefully select the material for a flipped classroom. They must choose whether, when, and how to change from classroom instruction and toward student-directed learning. They must also choose how to facilitate communication between students, or even between professors and students. Additionally, the teachers in flipped classrooms frequently evaluate their education and share with others in order to enhance it and to develop a shared knowledge of the specific idea taught in the format.

Learner's responsibility. Learners are urged to take control of their own learning when using a flipped learning strategy. Students in a flipped classroom are expected to support themselves and collaborate with their classmates in learning, which may be challenging for individuals who are used to sitting down to listen to lectures. In a flipped classroom, students are additionally required to discover the subject matter on their own. According to the learning chances offered by the teachers, they must also be able to improve their capacity for higher order thinking.

Teacher's position. The teachers' traditional "sage on the stage" position is generally replaced with "guide on the side" during the flipped classroom period. As a result, the teachers must be expert in the subject matter and have the ability to engage students. Teachers have more time to interact with all learners and actively participate as facilitators, coaches, mentors, or advisers to support learners inside the classroom because the flipped learning model gives the instruction outside of class time. Additionally, since students can learn at their own pace, teachers have more opportunities to provide feedback on each student's academic progress and to clarify any misunderstandings.

Additionally, teachers play crucial role in choosing authentic materials and producing content videos for learners. Teachers should also develop an alternative assessment for students to elicit and demonstrate their knowledge in accordance with the specified learning outcomes (Bergmann & Sams, 2012). Videos and real materials are frequently used in flipped learning environments in the classroom.

Material's role. They are the primary resources that are used to flip a typical classroom and contain the lessons and specific directions. In this situation, videos serve as excellent

learning resources that enable students to pursue independent learning outside of the classroom. Authentic materials, on the other hand, can be helpful and meaningful learning materials for both inside and outside the classroom activities in a flipped classroom (Bergmann et al., 2012; Bergmann & Sams, 2012; Driscoll, 2012; Khan, 2012; Pacansky-Brock, 2013). These materials include news articles, advertisements, movies, songs, TV broadcasts, newspapers, magazines, etc.

Conclusion. The flipped model provides a great an opportunity to enhance student's participation as well as self-study. Moreover, this approach can increase student's autonomous learning without depending on teachers. Since this model differs from traditional methods in terms of classroom activities. In terms of benefits, the flipped classroom provides teachers with more versatility in how they teach their lessons, allowing seminars to become more engaging and aimed at solving particular student weaknesses. One of the most significant advantages is the opportunity for increased interaction. Students, by far, stand to gain the most from the flipped classroom. This is because they can now study at their own pace, and review material, as needed – something that is not possible in a traditional classroom setting. Student success rates and attendance levels may also be affected.

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